

Self-ion irradiation of high purity iron: Unveiling plasticity mechanisms through nanoindentation experiments and large-scale atomistic simulations

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ABSTRACT

Ion irradiation may enhance material hardness through crystal defect nucleation and reorganization. In this study, we examine the nanomechanical behavior of high-purity iron samples, comparing the response of pristine specimen to those that have been self-irradiated with 5 MeV ions at 300°C. We utilize spherical nanoindentation to investigate the nanomechanical response, and we focus on the comprehensive modeling of the self-irradiation effects in high-purity iron through large-scale molecular simulations. Transmission electron microscopy is used in the irradiated regions, at various depths below the nanoindentation imprint, to analyze the nucleation of dislocation networks and the plastic deformation mechanisms at room temperature. Large scale novel molecular dynamics simulations are conducted to simulate overlapping collision cascades reaching an irradiation dose with defect density similar to experiments, followed by nanoindentation simulations that display qualitative agreement to experiments. We find that irradiated sample require higher critical load for the transition from elastic to plastic deformation due to interaction of dislocation lines with the dislocation loops and point defects formed during the irradiation, leading to hardening.

1. Introduction

Radiation-induced defects in materials can be generated through either neutron irradiation in a reactor core or ion irradiation in an ion accelerator facility. However, ion irradiation is an appealing option due to its ability to produce controlled displacement damage under well-defined conditions. Moreover, it has been demonstrated that ion irradiation can reproduce all the microstructural features seen in neutron-irradiated materials, such as dislocation loops, voids, bubbles, and radiation-induced solute segregation [1, 2, 3, 4]. This technology is a valuable and highly complementary tool to irradiation in a reactor, offering greater experimental control and ease of separation and study of individual phenomena, such as the impact of radiation-induced defects on dislocation nucleation and evolution. Importantly, ion irradiation does not activate the sample, making specimen handling much more straightforward and cost-effective. However, the damage region produced by the interaction of solid matter with ions is typically limited to a few micrometers at most, even for high-energy ions. Therefore, specialized techniques focused on probing small volumes of materials need to be developed to investigate their mechanical, structural, and thermal properties.

The defects in materials devoted to nuclear applications can occur at different scales, with mechanically induced micro-damage and radiation-induced nano-defects being two distinct origins. Mechanically induced micro-damage, such as micro-voids and micro-cracks, typically arises during manufacturing processes. For this reason, materials should be recrystallized. On the other hand, radiation-induced nano-defects result from the interaction of materials with radiation fields [5, 2]. The micro-deformation fields generated around mechanically induced micro-damage can impact the deformation of radiation-induced nano-defects. These micro-deformation fields exhibit directional response and strong anisotropic features, meaning they have preferential orientations and are sensitive to loading conditions [6]. As a result, micro-damage can influence the stress and strain fields in the vicinity, affecting the behavior of nearby nano-defects. The coupling between mechanically induced micro-damage and radiation-induced nano-defects is a complex phenomenon. It depends on various factors, such as defect density, defect size, and the characteristics of the radiative environment. The interaction between micro-damage and nano-defects can lead to stress concentration effects, alteration of local strain fields, and changes in the mobility and reactivity of nano-defects. This coupling mechanism becomes particularly crucial for materials located in radiative media. Irradiated materials experience radiation-induced defects, such as vacancies, interstitials, and dislocations at

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the nano- scale [5, 2]. Mechanically induced micro-damage can modify the local stress and strain fields around the nano-defects, influencing their stability, mobility, and interaction with the surrounding material. The impact of this coupling mechanism on the plastic deformation of irradiated materials is significant. The interaction between mechanically induced micro-damage and radiation-induced nano-defects can affect the overall deformation behavior, such as strain localization, crack initiation and propagation, and the overall strength and ductility of the material.

Nanoindentation has emerged as a powerful technique for investigating small volumes of ion-irradiated layers [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 5]. By driving a hard indenter of known geometry into a softer sample with a controlled load or displacement, we measure the dimensions of the resulting imprint and correlate them with hardness and Young's modulus. Recent advancements in testing equipment enable continuous control and monitoring of the indenter's loads and displacements during interactions with the sample material. One of the best examples available in the literature is those published by Heinze et al. [5, 14]. However, these investigations using Berkovich tips well describe problems during analysis and interpretation of nanoindentation results but lack the aspect of describing nanoindentation challenges with a different type of indenter. To address these limitations, our study focuses on exploring nanoindentation with different types of indenters, particularly the spherical indenter, shedding light on the analysis and phenomena observed in materials.

As the indentation depth decreases, new effects arise, and the local properties become depth and location dependent. These phenomena stem from local variations in the internal material structure and the inhomogeneous deformation strain experienced during indentations. In small indentation depths, where typically examine single-crystalline regions with low dislocation densities, uncovering intriguing phenomena such as dislocation nucleation. The indenter tip often approximated as spherical, induces a noticeable jump in the depth data known as a pop-in, which signifies the initiation of permanent plastic deformation beneath the indenter [15, 16].

A sharp indenter tip, due to its smaller radius of curvature, leads to a higher stress concentration at the tip when it contacts the material surface [17]. This concentrated stress can initiate local plastic deformation or even fracture in the material. As the applied indentation load increases, the stress at the tip intensifies, increasing the likelihood of surpassing the material's yield strength and resulting in pop-in. The higher stress concentration caused by the sharp indenter tip makes the material more susceptible to sudden displacement into the indented region. Using a larger indenter during indentation results in a broader coverage of the material's surface [18]. The expanded contact area induces a more extensive deformation field than a smaller indenter. The larger contact area leads to a higher volume of material undergoing plastic deformation, which increases the likelihood of pop-in. Additionally, the larger indenter generates higher

localized stresses, particularly at the edges of the contact region [19]. These heightened stresses further elevate the probability of pop-in occurring during indentation. While a sharp indenter tip and a larger indenter can increase the likelihood of pop-in, they also have advantages in specific testing scenarios. A sharp indenter tip provides better spatial resolution. It can help study a material's localized properties or small-scale features, e.g., grain or grain boundary [16]. A larger indenter, on the other hand, allows for averaging out local inhomogeneities and obtaining more representative bulk material properties [20].

Different size effects are primarily influenced by the ratio between the contact area and the size of the plastically deformed volume. Conical indentations with a constant self-similar profile show a decrease in hardness with increasing indentation depths. However, the situation becomes more intricate for spherical or cono-spherical indenter shapes, where the hardness increases after the pop-in event for a given sphere radius. This behavior can be attributed to the non-self-similar tip shape and the increasing strain experienced with indentation depth. Furthermore, when using spherical indenters with varying radii, the size of the sphere becomes the dominant factor, when larger spheres yielding larger contact areas for a given depth, resulting in higher locally observed hardness.

Furthermore, nanoindentation has proven valuable for study plasticity of materials, including the transition from the elastic to the plastic regime and other deformation mechanisms. This transition is characterized by a sudden displacement burst [21, 22], known as a pop-in event, which has been observed in previous studies [23, 24]. Before the pop-in, a high density of dislocations or a dislocation network is typically generated beneath the indenter tip. This accumulation arises due to the storage of elastic energy in the material, resulting from a scarcity of mobile defects capable of releasing the energy through plastic strain generation. The pop-in event is manifested as a sharp increase in load over a small depth on the load-displacement (L-D) curve. Subsequently, a catastrophic plasticity event occurs, involving homogeneous [25] or heterogeneous [26] dislocation nucleation from immobile defects, leading to a sudden release of the stored energy. This phenomenon is typically represented as a plateau in the L-D curves, indicating a sudden increase in depth under constant load. Multiple smaller pop-ins may follow, signifying further evolution of the dislocation network through dislocation avalanches. The origin of the pop-in phenomenon can have various causes, including crack nucleation and propagation [27, 28] or phase transitions [29]. The magnitude of the pop-in and the amount of stress needed to trigger the elastic to plastic transition depend on the structural features characteristic of the material, such as grain boundaries, precipitates, or point defects, which may block dislocation movement. By introducing radiation-induced defects to a material via ion irradiation, it is possible to investigate the plasticity of the ion-irradiated material using nanoindentation to probe small volumes. It is known that the elastic part of the load-displacement curves can

be fitted with the Hertz model for isotropic elastic contact. Therefore, the Hertz contact theory [30] provides a relationship between the applied load (P) and the resulting indentation depth (h) as:

$$P = \frac{4}{3} E_r \sqrt{R} h^{3/2}. \quad (1)$$

In this framework, the shear stress, τ , in the material at the elastic loading regime can be computed as follows [31]:

$$\tau = 0.31 \left(\frac{6PE_r^2}{\pi^3 R^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}, \quad (2)$$

where P is the load, E_r the reduced modulus, and R the tip radius. The evolution of dislocations can be further understood through computational models at different length–time scales being responsible for the material’s hardening [26]. This has been well documented for pristine Face Centered Cubic (FCC) and Body Centered Cubic (BCC) systems [32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37]. However, the complexity of these systems increases further for standard alloys, which are full of microstructural features. This is even more complicated because introduced radiation evolves over time and length scales [38]. For this reason, it is essential to build a solid understanding of the plasticity of a simple irradiated BCC system (e.g., pure Fe) and progress with microstructural complexity after an explanation of the mechanism in the simple system (for example, by studying Fe–Cr system).

Summarizing, this work aims to improve the understanding of plasticity in BCC systems, using experimental and Molecular Dynamics (MD) methods. In our work, the transition from elastic to plastic behavior is studied using nanoindentation, and the impact of plastic deformation on pristine and ion– irradiated materials is analyzed using Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). To emulate the experiments, molecular dynamics is used to simulate the effects of irradiation through overlapping collision cascades [39], resulting in a build-up of defects and radiation-induced dislocation nucleation. Large scale MD simulation [37, 33] are then employed to study the plastic deformation mechanism in pristine and irradiated iron, enabling us to observe atomic strain and displacements during the loading process and understand the nucleation and dynamics of dislocations, which contributes to material hardening.

2. Experimental and computational methods

2.1. Material

The high purity iron used in the study was cast by OCAS (Ghent, Belgium) and had a chemical composition listed in Tab. 1. The material was fabricated in a vacuum furnace by additive melting and made into a 10 mm thick rolled plate. The samples were cut from the material and polished on one side using a step-wise process with decreasing grain size of the polishing agent. The material has large globular shaped grains randomly distributed with an average size of around 90 μm and a fully ferritic microstructure, as shown in Fig. 1

by an Electron Backscatter Diffraction (EBSD) image of the pristine sample.

2.2. Ion irradiation

The ion irradiation experiment was conducted at the Ion Beam Center at Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR) using a 3 MV tandetron accelerator. Fe^{2+} ions with 5 MeV energy were used to irradiate the sample at 300°C. The temperature on the backside of the samples was monitored by a thermo–couple, and the sample was mounted on a heating target. The ion beam was focused to ensure uniform exposure over the irradiated area. The ion flux was continuously monitored to obtain the ion fluence. The profiles of displacements per atom (dpa) and injected interstitials (ipa) were calculated using the SRIM binary collision code [40] with a threshold displacement energy of 40 eV [41, 42]. The dpa and ipa profiles are displayed in Fig. 2 with the STEM image of the irradiated sample in the background to better visualize the material damage.

2.3. Nanoindentation technique

Nanomechanical investigations were carried out using a NanoTest Vantage system provided by Micro Materials Ltd. Measurements were done at room temperature with a spherical diamond indenter tip with a tip radius 25 μm . Indentations were performed in single force mode with a maximum load of 70 mN, and they were repeated at least 200 times on pristine and irradiated specimens. Loading, holding and unloading times were 25, 5, and 10 s, respectively. The distance between the indents was 40 μm . The number of pop-ins, along with the critical pop-in initiation load and pop-in

Table 1

Chemical composition of the iron samples.

Element	C	Cr	Ni	Si	P	Al	Fe
Weight %	<0.005	0.002	0.007	0.001	0.003	0.013	Bal.

Figure 1: EBSD IPF Z image of the pristine Fe sample

length, were determined and shown in Fig. 3. For clarity, occasional faulty trials were manually excluded.

2.4. Microstructure characterization (SEM/TEM)

Structural observations were performed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) Helios 5 UX provided by ThermoFisher Scientific. Electron transparent lamella of ion-irradiated material was prepared using the Focused Ion Beam (FIB) lift-out technique. Thinning was conducted with gradually decreasing beam acceleration to minimize the impact of Ga ions on dislocation structures. General observations of lamella were conducted under Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (STEM) mode. Detailed analysis was done on a Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) JEOL JEM 1200EX II system operated at 120 kV.

2.5. Atomistic model: Irradiated sample

The irradiated (011) Fe sample with lattice vectors [100] in x , [01-1] in y , and [011] in z is prepared through cumulative overlapping collision cascade simulations, reaching a dose of approximately 0.15 dpa by simulating 1000 consecutive 10 keV recoils at a temperature of 300°C. The dose is calculated with the NRT-dpa equation [43]. The simulation cell consisted of 642600 Fe atoms, which is large enough that the heat spikes generated by the 10 keV recoils were fully developed within the cell and that the periodic boundary conditions did not affect the final results. We employed established simulation methods for irradiation effects, including an adaptive time step algorithm, border cooling, electronic stopping power, and an interatomic potential (embedded atom method) fitted accurately for repulsion and defect properties [39, 44]. The electronic stopping power was accounted for as a friction force on atoms with kinetic energies above 10 eV, using stopping power data from SRIM- 2013 [45]. The simulations were performed with the LAMMPS code [46]. Border cooling and damping

Figure 2: Profiles of displacement damage (blue line) and concentration of injected interstitials (red line) for the 5 MeV Fe^{2+} -ion irradiation, obtained by SRIM calculations superimposed on the STEM image.

Figure 3: Typical load-displacement curves for pristine (black line) and ion irradiated (blue line) material with schematic illustration of a pop-in event identified by its critical load and length

of the cascade-induced shock waves was achieved by applying a thermostat on a 5 Å thick shell around the periodic borders of the cell. Each recoil was simulated for 20 ps, after which we applied the NPT ensemble on the entire cell for an additional 10 ps to allow for stress release and hence swelling. Between each recoil, the simulation cell was randomly shifted to achieve a homogeneous irradiation.

2.6. Atomistic model: Nanoindentation

We start by preparing the pristine (011) Fe sample with a density of 7.92 g/cm^3 which agrees well with the experimental data; with 11827815 Fe atoms in a (60, 62, 42) nm computer cell followed by applying the FIRE (fast inertial relaxation engine) 2.0 protocol [47] to optimize the energy of the sample and find the lowest energy structure. After that, an equilibration process is done for 100 ps using a Langevin thermostat at 77 and 300 K with a time constant of 100 fs [37, 33].

To study the effects of irradiation, a Fe sample was prepared at an irradiation dose of 0.15 dpa and replicated to match the size of the pristine sample. The replicated sample was subjected to a sequence of equilibration simulations with fully periodic boundary conditions to anneal the sample to 300 K, with each simulation lasting 5 ps. After this, a 5 nm vacuum section was added above the sample and the entire system was thermally equilibrated at room temperature for 20 ps until the sample reached a homogeneous temperature and pressure profile. This process was done to reach a stable temperature and pressure. In order to emulate nanoindentation test, the pristine and irradiated Fe samples are divided into three sections in the z direction to set up boundary conditions along its depth, dz : 1) a frozen section with a width of approximately $0.02 \times dz$, which was used for stability of the numerical cell; 2) a thermostatic section at approximately $0.08 \times dz$ above the frozen section, which

was used to dissipate the heat generated during nanoindentation [48]; and 3) a dynamical atoms section, where the interaction with the indenter tip modifies the surface structure of the samples. In addition, a 5 nm vacuum section was included at the top of the sample as an open boundary [33].

For the indenter tip, we utilize a non-atomic repulsive imaginary (RI) rigid sphere as our indenter tip, with radius $R = 12$ nm and a speed $v = 20$ m/s. Each calculation was performed for 125 ps with a time step of $\Delta t = 0.5$ fs. for a maximum indentation depth of 4.0 nm to avoid the influence of boundary layers of the material. The dislocation network is identified by using the DXA method [49] implemented in OVITO [50].

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Nanoindentation

Typical load-displacement curves for pristine (black line) and ion-irradiated materials (blue) recorded during indentation tests are shown in Fig. 3. Indentations were performed with the same load up to 70 mN. This resulted in deforming approx. 720 nm in the case of pristine and 650 nm in the case of ion irradiated material. One can observe that before pop-in effect occurs, the shape of the load-displacement (L-D) curves are identical for both specimens. It confirms that both samples possess the same density of dislocations and a similar number of pre-existing mobile dislocations. The investigated surface is free from discontinuities related to the polishing procedure and exhibits similar residual stress after being polished. This allows us to quantify and isolate the contribution of radiation damage to the hardening effect. This was proven by our previous studies using a Berkovich tip [51]. For example, Beake et al., [52] demonstrated that pop-ins developed in BCC tungsten are significantly reduced at high surface roughness. This study does not clarify if roughness itself or introduced defects are dominant in reducing the pop-in effect in BCC materials. Pöhl [16] confirmed this observation by subjecting a BCC iron specimen to aging at 150°C to promote carbon diffusion into the stress fields of the dislocations introduced during deformation. This treatment led to further suppression of pop-ins, providing additional evidence for the dominant role of surface roughness.

The region marked with a dotted orange line in Fig. 3 corresponds to a purely elastic response of the material which is of interest in our work. An elastic-to-plastic transition is observed in both samples once the critical point is reached. This behavior is typical for BCC materials and is consistent with experimental results [53, 52] and simulations [54, 55]. Notably, the irradiated sample requires a significantly higher load to initiate this transformation. This behavior suggests that the movement of dislocations generated due to deformation is hindered in the irradiated sample.

Deformation behavior in the irradiated sample is noticeably different from that of the pristine material. Our study

Figure 4: a) Linear correlation between pop-in initiation load and length of pop-in, b) The distribution of accumulated load at the initial pop-in event and the corresponding maximum shear stress determined through the Hertz model for pristine (black) and ion irradiated (blue) material.

focuses on visualizing the pop-in phenomena and establishing a correlation between the length of the pop-in event and the critical load. Figure 4a illustrates this correlation for both the pristine and irradiated samples. The black data points represent the pop-in magnitude in the pristine material, while the blue points indicate the behavior observed in the irradiated sample. Notably, a linear correlation between the load and pop-in length is observed in both cases. A significant distinction is evident between the pristine and irradiated materials throughout the entire load range. The slight scattering of results can be attributed to variations in the crystallographic orientations of probed grains, although the study did not specifically focus on the influence of grain boundaries. Regarding the static behavior, the ion-irradiated material demonstrates a more consistent response. In general, the pristine material requires a lower critical load (i.e., lower energy) to initiate a pop-in event, and the measured pop-in length is typically shorter compared to the irradiated material.

In Fig. 4b, we present the distribution of the accumulated critical load at the initial pop-in event and the corresponding maximum shear stress calculated using the Hertz model

for pristine (black) and ion irradiated (blue) materials. The shear stress is determined by considering the initial pop-in event as a transition from elastic to plastic deformation, utilizing Eq.2. The calculated shear stresses are 1.62 ± 0.38 GPa for the pristine and 2.01 ± 0.23 GPa for the irradiated material. The critical shear stress required for homogeneous dislocation nucleation is within the range $G/5$ and $G/30$ [18, 56, 57] for crystalline metals, with G being the shear modulus. For iron, with a shear modulus of 80.7 GPa [16], the critical value is expected to be between 2.69–16.4 GPa. However, the observed difference in shear stress between the pristine and irradiated materials is likely influenced by the Indentation Size Effect (ISE), as reported in previous studies [18, 58, 52, 17, 59]. The ISE refers to the decrease in shear stress with an increase in indenter radius, attributed to the higher probability of encountering existing dislocations as the indenter size increases. When using a small indenter, such as Berkovich, there is a greater likelihood of probing a volume of material without pre-existing dislocations, leading to plastic deformation occurring only after reaching the theoretical stress threshold and nucleating new dislocations. Conversely, a larger indenter increases the chance of pre-existing dislocations aiding in the initiation of plasticity. It is important to note that the shear stress values presented in 4b do not represent the true critical shear stress required for homogeneous dislocation nucleation, but rather offer an estimation of the contribution originating from irradiation. In the irradiated sample, the critical load and shear stress measurements are typically higher than those of the non-irradiated sample. This behavior can be attributed to the presence of radiation-induced defects or interstitial atoms, and the accumulation of residual stress [60]. During the ion irradiation process, carbon atoms can diffuse into stress fields around existing dislocations, forming a Cottrell atmosphere and subsequent dislocation pinning [61, 62]. This phenomenon has been observed in transmission electron microscopy (TEM) data and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, providing further insights into dislocation nucleation and pinning mechanisms. Moreover, while nanoindentation pop-ins and yield drops during tensile testing occur at different length scales, they both represent manifestations of strain softening and may have a fundamental relationship with each other. Dislocations trapped by solute atmospheres can break free at the upper yield point, resulting in instantaneous softening and a sharp drop in yield strength. Subsequently, as the load is released and the specimen is allowed to rest, solute atoms diffuse to the dislocations, leading to a decrease in mobile dislocation density and the reappearance of the yield point, a phenomenon known as strain aging [63].

3.2. Microstructure characterization

To investigate microstructural changes caused by plastic deformation and the ion irradiation process, four-electron transparent lamellas were prepared using a FIB lift-out technique. The pristine sample, taken from the non-deformed region, is illustrated in Fig. 5a-c. The performed microstructural investigations reveal the occurrence of the individual

dislocation lines (marked with blue arrows) with a relatively low density. It is noteworthy that such dislocation are typical and inherent to the material's production process [5, 6]. Fig. 5d-f show the microstructure of the pristine sample in the area below the indent indicating the propagation of dislocation lines (indicated by blue arrows) resulting from plastic deformation. Deformation-induced dislocations manifest as relatively elongated lines that glide along the slip planes. To aid comprehension of the observed phenomena, the depth of the damage peak in the implanted sample is denoted in yellow. Additionally, a close-up view of the area at a depth of approximately $1.3 \mu\text{m}$ is presented in Fig. 5f. Dislocations below this depth exhibit a tangled configuration, indicating their movement and interaction. In certain instances, these dislocations agglomerate to form slightly larger dislocation lines. The calculated average of all depth dislocation density of this material is $1.66 \times 10^{14} \left(\frac{1}{\text{m}^2}\right)$.

Another two lamellas were cut from ion-irradiated material. The microstructure of the non-deformed region are shown in Fig. 6, whereas the microstructure of the region below the indent in Fig. 7. In both cases, the indents located in the central area of the grain, far from grain boundaries, were chosen for the investigations. The studied area covered the zone below the indent, including the radiation damage peak, which is located at about $1.3 \mu\text{m}$ depth. In addition to that, we investigated the area about $1 \mu\text{m}$ below the damage peak. For further clarification, see Fig. 2, where the SRIM profile has been superimposed with the STEM image. It is crucial to emphasize that ion irradiation leads to the formation of band-like microstructure [5]. Indeed, the dark band (between blue lines) in the Fig. 6a corresponds to a high concentration of small dislocation loops. Dislocation loops are observable as circular or elliptical features (yellow arrows) on Fig. 6e-f, providing valuable insights into the crystal lattice imperfections in ion irradiated materials. These dislocations are typical effect of ion-irradiation process [3, 2, 4, 33].

A general image representing the area under the indent in the ion-irradiated sample is present in Fig. 7a, while a detailed description is shown in Fig. 7b-h. The microstructural analysis of the irradiated material revealed numerous well known defects induced by deformation and radiation damage, such as dislocation loops [33, 3, 4, 5] and dislocation lines, as seen in Fig. 7. Dislocation loops act as an obstacles in movement of dislocations lines thus their presence may not be clear at first glance. Deformation-induced dislocations are relatively long lines which glide on the slip planes until their motion is restricted by other defects. Fig. 7d-f (blue, orange and violet arrows) clearly indicates such interaction as curvy dislocation lines which seem to be pinned at irradiation-induced dislocation loops. Considering the area near the surface of the sample (see Fig. 7b-d), mainly the dislocation lines can be observed. One can observe that the density of dislocations seems to steadily increase with increasing depth from the surface of the sample. This observation was confirmed by the calculations of the density of dislocation lines presented in Fig.8. The maximum density of dislocation lines were observed at depth

Figure 5: Cross-sectional a) STEM b,c) TEM images of the pristine material with marked dislocation lines (blue arrows) d) cross-sectional STEM image, e) TEM image f) magnification at the depth around $1.3 \mu\text{m}$ on dislocation lines in plastically deformed pristine material. Dislocation lines are marked with blue arrows.

of $1.1\text{--}1.3 \mu\text{m}$, which corresponded to the area of highest damage. Fig. 7 e,f) shows magnification of this region, and one can observe extensive interactions between dislocation lines and irradiation defects. Tiny dislocation loops formed at possible slip systems. Since in BCC lattice all slip systems share the same Burger vector type – $a/2\langle 111 \rangle$ – pinned defects cannot easily release themselves what ultimately lead to a significant hardening effect. The observed density of dislocation lines is steady increasing with the depth as the number of possible pinning points (irradiation– induced dislocation loops) is also increasing with radiation damage up to a Bragg peak at approximately $1.3 \mu\text{m}$ depth. This phenomena explains the increased hardness of the irradiated material as was determine using the nanoindentation technique. The interaction of the dislocation lines with the pre– existing irradiation defects during the deformation leading to the increase of the dislocation density in this area and therefore the hardening of the material. In the final part of our work, we focused on the plastic deformation region below the Bragg peak, where no radiation damage is expected. However, we found that this region is still affected by

plastic deformation (see Fig. 7 g,h). The dislocation density in this region appears to be smaller compared to the area just below the indents. Moreover, the dislocations in this region are generally tangled, indicating their movement and interaction. In some cases, the dislocations form slightly larger dislocation lines.

3.3. Computational model

In order to confirm the experimental observations, thorough molecular simulations have been implemented. In Fig.9, we display the outcome of nucleated defects and dislocations at an irradiation dose of 0.15 dpa . The main type of dislocation loops produced by continuous irradiation are interstitial-type with a Burgers vector of $1/2\langle 111 \rangle$, while $\langle 100 \rangle$ loops are also formed, as reported in previous work [39, 64]. Furthermore, it is also consistent with previous work, where small C15 Laves phase interstitial clusters formed, shown in yellow in Fig. 9. C15-like clusters are energetically the most stable self-interstitial cluster in iron at small sizes, and the interatomic potential we used can clearly reproduce [65, 39]. The sample in Fig.9 is then replicated to

Figure 6: Cross-sectional a) Cross-sectional STEM image of ion irradiated material with marked peak damage (dash blue lines), e,f) magnification of the irradiated region with marked (yellow arrows) dislocation loops.

Figure 7: a)STEM observations of ion irradiated specimen with marked (dashed color lines) TEM cross section b)cross-sectional TEM images of the region next to the indentation mark, and c,d) around the irradiated region. e,f) A magnification of the irradiated region. g,h) Material under the Bragg peak. We identify dislocation lines and loops nucleated due to nanoindentation and irradiation mechanism. Pinned dislocation are marked with arrows.

Figure 8: Density of dislocation lines distribution in the cross-section of the ion-irradiated sample

Figure 9: (Color on-line) Visualization of nucleated defects and dislocation loops in the [011] Fe sample, due to consecutive overlapping collision cascades with PKA energies of 10 keV at a temperature of 300°C. This sample is utilized for nanoindentation simulations.

match the required dimensions for nanoindentation simulations presented in Sec 2.6.

In Fig. 10, we report the ratio of mean contact pressure, p_m , of pristine and irradiated Fe matrices to the Young modulus, E_Y , calculated in terms of linear elastic contact mechanics [32, 34]:

$$\frac{p_m}{E_{klm}} = \frac{2\pi}{3E_{klm}} \left[24P \left(\frac{E_{klm}R}{1-\nu^2} \right)^2 \right]^{1/3}, \quad (3)$$

as a function of the normalized contact radius, a/R , between the sample and the tip with the geometrical relationship $a(h) = [3PR(1-\nu^2)/8E_{klm}]^{1/3}$ which is related to the inner radius of the plastic region where the defects nucleate. We present the average of 10 MD simulations computed as $\bar{p} = 1/N \sum_i p_i$ where N is the number of performed

simulations. For the irradiated case, the Young's modulus is found by fitting the load curve to the Hertz fitting [66, 35].

The average results \bar{p}/E_Y , for the elastic part of the loading process follow the universal linear relationship as [32]: $0.844/(1-\nu^2)a/R_i$ showing the typical linear elastic contact mechanics which assures that boundary conditions do not affect the simulation dynamics. Surface morphology due to sample preparation are observed in the elastic part by fluctuations of the mean contact as response of the interaction of the indenter tip with the Fe atoms at the top layer of the surface sample. We have added a colored region that displays the minimum and maximum normalized contact pressure from our simulations versus strain. This indicates that the critical load for the pop-in event in the irradiated sample is higher than the pristine case, consistent with experimental results (See Fig. 4-6). In the computational modeling this difference is characterized as $\Delta p = 0.022E_Y$ at this irradiation dose. We assume an isotropic Hertzian contact model to estimate the maximum shear stress from the contact pressure calculations[67]. The maximum shear stress under the indenter tip (τ_{Max}) is then computed as $\tau_{Max} = 0.31p_0$, where p_0 represents the maximum value of contact pressure under the indenter tip. p_0 is obtained from the mean contact pressure (p_m) as $p_0 = 1.5 \max(p_m)$ [67, 68]. Thus the obtained values for the pristine case is 10.35 ± 1.0 GPa and 10.79 ± 1.05 GPa for the irradiated one, where the difference $\Delta\tau_{Max} \sim 0.44$ is into the order of the experimental results by considering ISE and the MD limitations.

Based on our MD simulations, we have identified two mechanisms contributing to the observed increase in critical load during the pop-in event in the irradiated Fe sample. These mechanisms are as follows: i) Vacancy-assisted expansion: Vacancies generated from irradiation can influence the behavior of half loops. In this scenario, a half loop

Figure 10: (Color on-line) Average contact pressure normalized by the Young's modulus as a function of the nanoindentation strain. The results show a higher pop-in load for the irradiated sample than the one presented for the pristine case, in fair agreement with experimental data.

Figure 11: (Color online) Visualization of dislocation nucleation and dynamics during the loading process in a-b), and after unloading the tip in c). Identification of typical dislocation mechanisms are indicated and labeled.

can expand in size to accommodate and overcome the presence of these vacancies. This expansion allows the dislocation to continue propagating, contributing to the increased critical load. ii) Interaction with irradiation-induced loops: Another mechanism involves the interaction between half and irradiation-induced loops. A jog dislocation is formed when a half loop encounters an existing loop created by the irradiation process. This interaction alters the dislocation structure and affects the deformation behavior, resulting in an increased critical load for the pop-in event.

In Figure. 11, we depict the dislocation nucleation and dynamics during loading a-b) and after removal of the indenter tip c) by comparing pristine and irradiated samples. The samples were cut at the plane (01-1) for better visualization of the dislocations and defects; the indenter tip is represented by a dashed line; small voids are depicted by gray shapes for the irradiated sample; and a 5 nm scale reference is included. A general characteristic of the comparison between pristine and irradiated samples, is the fact that irradiated nanoindentation-induced plastic zone is quite more extended (by up to 10x) than what it is for the pristine case. This is a natural outcome of the fact that irradiated samples contain a wealth of pre-existing defects that can drive deformation-induced dislocation loop nucleation as nanoindentation loads are applied, and is in qualitative consistency with experimental observations (see Fig.7).

In Fig. 11a, for the pristine case the indenter tip penetrates a distance of 2 nm and nucleates shear loops which propagate along the $\langle 011 \rangle$ slip plane. These loops expand due to the advancement of edge components, while screw

components undergo limited cross-slip, leading to a pinching off reaction and nucleation of a prismatic loop, commonly observed for pristine Fe matrix with $[011]$. In the irradiated case, a similar mechanism occurs, but screw pinch-off loops form only in areas with low vacancy density. Sometimes, shear loops encounter preexisting dislocation loops with a Burgers vector of $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$, which suppresses the formation of screw pinch-off loops. From our MD simulations, it is also observed that during early stages of loading, preexisting irradiation-induced loops tend to be adsorbed by the plastic region created by the indenter tip, suppressing nanoindentation-induced nucleation of prismatic loops.

In Fig. 11b, the results of the simulation at a depth of 2.5 nm, where the indenter tip has reached its maximum penetration, are presented. For the pristine sample, two prismatic loops are observed to have formed as a result of the evolution of screw pinch-off loops during loading. In the irradiated sample, a shear loop nucleated due to the nanoindentation-induced dislocation mechanism interacts with a pre-existing prismatic loop caused by the irradiation process, which has a partially formed $\langle 001 \rangle$ junction. It is also noted that small voids and loops present prior to loading are being displaced, and some of these loops interact with each other to form larger ones, which contributes to the hardening of the material.

In Fig. 11c, we display the results after removing the indenter tip. In the pristine case, the reversible process causes the shear loops and half loops to be absorbed by the surface, resulting in two prismatic loops in the sample. For the irradiated sample, the relaxation time of 1 ps after the nanoindentation test allows the material to recover, as observed near the surface where the density of dislocation

loops created by irradiation decreases and bigger loops form deeper in the sample due to the interaction of shear loops and pre-existing radiation-induced loops. However, some irradiation loops that did not interact with indentation dislocations may still interact during the nanoindentation process, as seen at the bottom part of the surface. This figure aligns well with TEM images, which show the formation of new dislocation loops (resulting from the interaction between irradiation and indentation) that can lead to the formation of large dislocation lines (see Fig. 7). The pinning of dislocations may be due to the presence of C atoms in the sample resulting from ion irradiation, but this is outside the scope of the numerical modeling.

4. Concluding remarks

In this study, we investigated the dislocation mechanisms occurring during spherical nanoindentation of pristine and self-irradiated high-purity Fe samples with a body-centered cubic (BCC) crystal structure. The self-irradiated samples were prepared through experimental irradiation using Fe^{2+} ions at 5 MeV and 300°C, as well as through molecular dynamics simulations simulating overlapping collision cascades resulting in a dose of 0.15 displacements per atom (dpa). Our findings reveal that the critical loads and shear stress values required for the transition from elastic to plastic deformation were higher, on average, for the irradiated material compared to the pristine material. That was corroborated by experiments and MD simulations. This phenomenon can be attributed to the formation of dislocation loops and point defects induced by irradiation, which interacted with the dislocations generated during nanoindentation, occasionally impeding the propagation of conventional screw pinch loops and shear loops within the plastic region. Consequently, this mechanism contributed to the higher critical loads and enhanced material hardening. To further investigate this behavior, we characterized four samples using Transmission Electron Microscopy, which provided valuable insights into the nucleation of dislocation networks and experimental observations of plastic deformation mechanisms. These findings were further supported by large-scale molecular dynamics simulations employing a spherical indenter tip, allowing us to visualize nucleated dislocation networks' dynamic evolution and interaction with pre-existing dislocation loops induced by irradiation. In conclusion, our study highlights the significance of comprehending the mechanisms underlying plastic deformation in assessing radiation damage in nuclear materials. The outcomes of this research offer valuable information that could aid in developing novel materials with superior mechanical properties and enhanced resistance to radiation.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

K. Mulewska: Conceptualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Data curation, Writing—original draft, Writing—Review & Editing. **F. J. Dominguez-Gutierrez:** Writing—original draft, Writing—Review & Editing, Software, Visualization. **D. Kalita:** Investigation, Writing—Review & Editing. **J. Byggmästar:** Writing - Review & Editing, Software. **G.Y. Wei:** Investigation. **W. Chromiński:** Investigation, Writing—Review & Editing. **S. Papanikolaou:** Supervision, Writing—Review & Editing. **M. J. Alava:** Supervision. **Ł. Kurpaska:** Writing—Review & Editing, Supervision. **J. Jagielski:** Supervision.

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